

OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPMENT AND IMPROVEMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION SERVICES

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Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'limda ta'lim xizmatlarini rivojlantirishda professor-o'qituvchilarning pedagogik faoliyatini takomillashtirish maqsadida talabalar o'rtasida o'tkazilgan onlayn so'rovnoma natijalari tahlil qilindi hamda tegishli takliflar berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: oliy ta'lim, ta'lim xizmatlari, pedagogik faoliyat, ta'lim sifati, dars jarayoni, zamonaviy bilim.

Abstract: This article analyzed the results of an online survey conducted among students to improve the pedagogical activity of professors and teachers in the development of educational services in higher education, and relevant suggestions were made.

Keywords: Higher education, educational services, professors and teachers, pedagogical activity, quality of education, teaching process, modern knowledge.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализированы результаты онлайн-опроса, проведенного среди студентов с целью улучшения педагогической деятельности профессорско-преподавательского состава в развитии образовательных услуг в высшей школе, и внесены соответствующие предложения.

Ключевые слова: Высшее образование, образовательные услуги, профессорско-преподавательский состав, педагогическая деятельность, качество образования, учебный процесс, современные знания.

The future of our country and the development of the nation directly depends on the level of education. Due to this, great importance is attached to the development of education in our country. As our President noted, the greatest institution is an educational institution, and the greatest profession is the profession of a pedagogue. Taking this into account, on October 9, 2019, President Sh.M. Mirziyoev signed the Decree "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030"¹. This Concept consists of 4 chapters, which reflect the following: general rules, the current state of the higher education system in our republic and existing problems, strategic goals and priorities for the

development of the higher education system, and the expected results from the implementation of the Concept in the future. 1 National database of legal documents, 09.10.2019, No. 06/19/5847/3887. "Possibilities of using digital and innovative technologies in the development of the service sector and poverty reduction" Materials of the National Institute of Higher Education 260 The main task of higher education – consists of training highly qualified specialists with high spiritual, cultural, and moral qualities who can solve the issue of scientific-technical, socio-economic and cultural development of Uzbekistan at the level of developed countries.

Consulting services in the field of higher education are educational services that provide potential consumers with the necessary information resources that allow them to perform their tasks more effectively in a certain professional activity [1].

Consulting services in higher educational institutions can be classified as follows (Table 1).

Table 1

Classification of consulting services in higher education institutions.

Activities of higher education institutions	Types of consulting services
Educational activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • consulting on educational subjects; • in-depth study of special subjects outside the curriculum; • improvement and retraining of personnel; • Training
Scientific activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • participation in grant contests; • creating licensed services; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • patenting; • conduct scientific research on the announced topic; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • preparation of scientific reports; • preparation of scientific articles and monographs;
Expert activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • preparation of expert opinions on various objects, and types of activities; • development of recommendations according to the requirements of organizations, and enterprises.

Consulting services in the field of higher education belong to the type of "B2B" ("business-to-business") services aimed at organizing work with partners. In addition, consulting services are very widely developed in the form of "B2G" services ("business-to-government"), because the state, as the largest investor, is an active consumer of educational consulting services and actively cooperates with higher education institutions [2].

It is necessary to create a system that ensures the transfer of knowledge and technologies from the environment of HEIs to production for regular use of the knowledge obtained as a result of scientific and intellectual activities of HEIs for commercial purposes. Such a system can be focused on attracting private investments to encourage higher education institutions to create innovative inventions, increase the number of patents issued for these inventions, and support scientific and intellectual activities in the field of higher education.

To achieve the above goals, it is possible to widely use directions such as increasing the share of consulting services in the total volume of educational services in higher education institutions, strengthening the brand of consulting departments of higher education institutions, and improving the quality of consulting services in the field of higher education.

In the implementation of measures aimed at the development of consulting services, the main attention should be focused on solving issues such as improving the efficiency of consulting services, identifying customers and markets, and encouraging the consulting activities of professors and teachers [3].

The analysis shows that in many institutions that provide educational services, the economic justification of management decisions is weak. In these institutions, the quality and content of the organization of the educational process are prioritized over the economic principles of management. Although these processes should be implemented equally, effective management is essential for modern HEIs[4].

- In summary, educational consulting services provide many opportunities to expand the scope of services such as:
- receiving high-quality consulting services that help solve practical problems of the enterprise based on the introduction of modern knowledge and management methods;
- integrating the results of scientific research into the management activities of enterprises to improve the quality and efficiency of management decisions;
- development of the infrastructure of consulting services in higher education institutions;
- enrichment of the practical experience of users of consulting services with information base and methodological knowledge.

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